

Numerical Investigation on Mechanical Properties of Polymer Composites Reinforced with MXene Nanosheets

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Motivation, Aim, Method

Motivation. A new class of 2D nanomaterials MXenes was discovered [1]. MXenes behave as “conductive clays” because of the combination of the metallic conductivity of transition metal carbides and the hydrophilic nature of their hydroxyl or oxygen terminated surfaces [2]. MXenes have already found various applications. However, the possibilities of this material as a filler for nano-engineered structural polymer composites have not been studied yet.

Aim. This study is addressed to identify a suitable methodology based on finite element (FE) homogenization approach for prediction of mechanical properties of polymer composite reinforced with MXene 2D nanosheets.

Method. The FE analysis of mechanical behaviour of Epoxy/MXene composite was performed by DIGIMAT™ and ABAQUS.

FE Model Generation

Representative volume elements (RVEs) of Epoxy/MXene nanocomposites

Mechanical Behaviour of Epoxy/MXene Composite

Stress in Epoxy/Mxene 3D RVEs: (a) 10 wt% random; (b) 30 wt% aligned [3]

MXene volume fraction, orientation and aspect ratio AR influence on the stress – strain relationship of Epoxy/MXene nanocomposite

Conclusions

- The model calibration was performed with Epoxy/MXene experimental tests.
- The strength properties of the interphase layer after an inverse modelling were assumed to be the same as the matrix.
- The model with aligned multilayered MXenes showed higher strength and elastic properties than random one.
- The higher volume fraction and aspect ratio of aligned multilayered MXenes significantly increases Young modulus and strength of the nanocomposite.

References

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